

The background of the cover features an aerial photograph of a river winding through a dry, brown landscape. The river is a vibrant blue-green color, contrasting with the surrounding arid terrain. In the bottom right corner, there is a stylized, glowing blue data visualization consisting of a grid of points and lines, resembling a topographical map or a data network. The overall color palette is dominated by dark blues and browns.

International Scientific and Practical Conference

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO WATER RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN ARID REGIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE

PROCEEDINGS
(Conference Proceedings)

May 19, 2026

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

WICAR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

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International Scientific and Practical Conference -2026

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO WATER RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN ARID REGIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference innovative approaches to water resource management in arid regions in the context of climate change on May 19, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The conference aims to discuss key issues of effective water resource management in arid regions under climate change, develop and apply innovative approaches and mathematical and computational modeling methods, share recent research results and practical experience, and strengthen international academic cooperation in this field.

Key Themes of the Conference:

1. Water Diplomacy and Integrated Approaches in International Relation: Interdisciplinary Approaches to Sustainable Development, Communication and Global Security

- Issues of systemic analysis in international relations and world politics in the context of water diplomacy
- Economic, environmental and energy aspects of sustainable development
- Systemic approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

2. Mathematical and computer modeling of optimal water resources management under climate change

- Optimal water resource management under climate change
- Modeling water resource dynamics and climate variability
- Methods of applied and computational mathematics in irrigation system modeling.

3. Environmental and Hydrogeological Processes in the Aral Sea Region: Analysis Based on Modern Technologies

- Analysis of hydrogeological processes in the Aral Sea region
- Application of artificial intelligence, machine learning, and big data technologies to environmental challenges
- Simulation and stochastic modeling of environmental and hydrogeological processes in the Aral region.

The event was conducted in a hybrid format with participation in English, Russian, and Uzbek. The conference provided a high-level platform for scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Nasos stansiyalar ishini optimal boshqarish masalasini chekli ayirmalar usuli bilan yechish

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Annotatsiya. Maqola, nasos stansiyalarining ishini optimal boshqarish masalasi haqida bo'lib, ayniqsa, energetika sarfini minimallashtirish nuqtai nazaridan, chekli ayirmalar usuli orqali yechishga oid metodik yondashuv taqdim etilgan. Maqsad – suv ta'minoti tizimlarini samarali boshqarish uchun nasos stansiyalarning optimal ish rejimlarini tanlash va energiya sarfini kamaytirish hisoblanadi. Hamda maqolada nasos stansiyalari ishini optimal boshqarish masalasining matematik modeli ishlab chiqilganligi, suv sathi o'zgarishi chekli ayirmalar usuli asosida diskretlashtirilib energiya sarfini kamaytirishga qaratilgan maqsad funksiyasi shakllantirilganligi keltirilgan. Shuningdek, modelda nasoslarning maksimal suv uzatish imkoniyati, rezervuardagi suv sathining minimal va maksimal chegaralari, iste'molchilar talabi hamda nasoslarning ish rejimiga oid cheklovlar hisobga olinganligi maqolada ta'kidlab o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Nasos stansiyalari, optimal boshqaruv, chekli ayirmalar usuli, energiya sarfi, suv sathi, diskret optimallashtirish.

Kirish. Hozirgi kunda suv resurslaridan oqilona foydalanish, irrigatsiya tizimlarining samaradorligini oshirish hamda elektr energiyasi sarfini kamaytirish qishloq xo'jaligi va suv xo'jaligi sohalarining dolzarb masalalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Ayniqsa, sug'oriladigan yerlar ulushi yuqori bo'lgan hududlarda suvni belgilangan vaqtda, kerakli miqdorda va zarur bosimda yetkazib berish nasos stansiyalarining barqaror va samarali ishlashiga bevosita bog'liqdir. Nasos stansiyalarida elektr energiyasi iste'moli katta ulushni tashkil etgani sababli ularning ish rejimini optimal boshqarish iqtisodiy va texnik jihatdan muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Nasos stansiyalarining an'anaviy boshqaruv usullarida ko'pincha nasos agregatlari oldindan belgilangan jadval asosida yoki operator tajribasiga tayangan holda ishga tushiriladi va to'xtatiladi. Bunday yondashuv har doim ham suv talabining vaqt bo'yicha o'zgarishini, rezervuar yoki kanal tizimidagi suv sathini, elektr energiyasi tariflaridagi farqlarni hamda nasoslarning texnik imkoniyatlarini to'liq hisobga olmaydi. Natijada ortiqcha energiya sarfi, suvning samarasiz taqsimlanishi, nasos uskunalarning tez eskirishi va ekspluatatsion xarajatlarning oshishi kuzatilishi mumkin.

Shu sababli nasos stansiyalarining ishini matematik modellashtirish va optimal boshqarish usullari asosida tashkil etish zarurati ortib bormoqda. Optimal boshqaruv masalasida asosiy maqsad - iste'molchilar talabini qondirgan holda nasos agregatlarining energiya sarfini minimallashtirish, tizimdagi suv sathi va bosim ko'rsatkichlarini ruxsat etilgan chegaralarda saqlash hamda nasoslarning ish rejimini texnik jihatdan maqbul holatda tanlashdan iboratdir. Bunda suv balansi, nasoslarning unumdorligi, elektr energiyasi narxi, rezervuar hajmi, suv iste'moli grafigi va boshqa omillar o'zaro bog'liq holda qaraladi.

Mazkur masalani yechishda chekli ayirmalar usuli samarali sonli yondashuvlardan biri sifatida qo'llanilishi mumkin. Ushbu usul yordamida nasos stansiyasi ishini ifodalovchi differensial tenglamalar vaqt bo'yicha diskret ko'rinishga keltiriladi. Natijada uzluksiz boshqaruv jarayoni alohida vaqt bosqichlarida tahlil qilinadi va har bir bosqich uchun nasoslarning ish holati, suv sarfi, suv sathi hamda energiya xarajatlari aniqlanadi. Bu esa murakkab gidravlik va energetik

jarayonlarni kompyuter yordamida hisoblash, taqqoslash va optimal yechimni tanlash imkonini beradi [1,3].

Asosiy qism.

Masalaning qo'yilishi: Sug'orish tizimlarining samaradorligini oshirish, energiya resurslarini tejash va resurslardan oqilona foydalanish muhimligini inobatga olib, suv ta'minoti va energetika sohalarida qo'llanilishi mumkin. Energiya narxlari va suv talabining o'zgaruvchanligi davrida ushbu yondashuvlar iqtisodiy jihatdan muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'ladi bu esa mavzuning dolzarbligini bildiradi. Shu munosabat bilan nasos stansiyasining ishini optimal boshqarish asosan minimal elektr energiya sarfi bilan iste'molchilarga zarur suv bosimi va suv hajmini yetkazib berishdan iborat.

Asosiy masalalar:

1. *Nasos stansiyalarining boshqaruvi:* Suv ta'minoti tizimlarida nasoslar yordamida suv sathi va bosimning doimiy ravishda nazorat qilinishi zarur. Nasoslar soni va ish holati vaqt davomida o'zgariishi mumkin. Bu holatni optimal ravishda boshqarish uchun matematik model ishlab chiqiladi.

2. *Chekli ayirmalar usuli:* Uzlüksiz vaqt davomida bo'lib turadigan boshqaruv masalasi, vaqtni diskretlashtirish orqali **chekli ayirmalar usuli** yordamida yechiladi. Vaqt oralig'i diskret bosqichlarga bo'linadi, suv sathining hosilasi chekli ayirma bilan ifodalanadi va shu orqali boshqaruv parametrlarini hisoblash uchun algebraik tenglamalar tuziladi.

3. *Energiya sarfini minimallashtirish:* Maqsadli funktsiya sifatida **energiya xarajatlari** olinadi. Elektr energiyasining sarfini kamaytirish uchun, nasoslarning ish rejimlari optimal tarzda tanlanadi. Maqolada energiya tariflari o'zgarishini inobatga olish, nasoslarni tez-tez yoqib-o'chirishning mexanik eskirishga olib kelishini hisobga olish zarurligi ta'kidlanadi.

4. *Diskret masala va cheklovlar:* Har bir vaqt bosqichida nasoslarning holatini aniqlash, suv sathi va bosim cheklovlari, talabni ta'minlash uchun suyuqlik oqimini hisoblashga qaratilgan. Suv sathining minimal va maksimal chegaralari, nasosning maksimal chiqish quvvati va energiya sarfi bo'yicha cheklovlar qo'yiladi.

5. *Matematik modellar va yechimlar:* Nasos stansiyasining ishini optimallashtirish uchun matematik modeldan foydalaniladi, u quyidagi shartlarni hisobga oladi: suv sathi cheklovlari, nasoslarning ish rejimlari va energiya sarfi. Chekli ayirmalar usuli yordamida bu model diskretizatsiya qilinadi va optimallashtiriladi [9,10].

Optimal boshqaruv masalasida boshqaruv o'zgaruvchisi quyidagicha yoziladi:

$$u_i(t) \quad (1)$$

bu yerda:

$$u_i(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & i - \text{agregat ishlaydi} \\ 0, & i - \text{agregat ishlamaydi} \end{cases}$$

Agar nasos tezligi rostlanadigan bo'lsa:

$$0 \leq u_i(t) \leq 1$$

deb olinadi.

Dinamik model. Rezervuardagi suv balansi quyidagicha yoziladi:

$$\frac{dh(t)}{dt} = \frac{1}{S} \left(\sum_{i=1}^m Q_i(t) - D(t) \right) \quad (2)$$

bu yerda $h(t)$ -suv sathi, $Q_i(t)$ - i -agregat uzatayotgan suv sarfi, $D(t)$ - iste'molchilar talabi, S - rezervuar yuzasi, T -boshqaruv davri [10].

Bu tenglama shuni bildiradi:

- agar agregatlar uzatayotgan suv miqdori talabdan katta bo'lsa, suv sathi oshadi;
- agar talab katta bo'lsa, suv sathi pasayadi.

Maqsad funksiya - Optimal boshqaruvning asosiy maqsadi elektr energiya sarfini kamaytirishdir:

$$J = \int_0^T C(t) \sum_{i=1}^m P_i(t) dt \rightarrow \min \quad (3)$$

bu yerda J - umumiy xarajat, $C(t)$ - elektr energiya ta'rifi, $P_i(t)$ - i - nasosning quvvati, m - nasoslar soni [6,10].

Nasos quvvati odatda quyidagicha hisoblanadi:

$$P_i(t) = \frac{\rho g Q_i(t) H_i(t)}{\eta_i}$$

bu yerda ρ - suv zichligi, g - erkin tushish tezlanishi, $Q_i(t)$ - suv sarfi, $H_i(t)$ - nasos bosimi, η_i - foydali ish koeffitsiyenti [5].

Demak, (3) maqsad funksiyasini quyidagicha yozib olamiz:

$$J = \int_0^T C(t) \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{\rho g Q_i(t) H_i(t)}{\eta_i} dt \rightarrow \min \quad (3^*)$$

Optimal boshqaruv masalasida faqat energiyani kamaytirish emas. Suv ta'minoti ham barqaror bo'lishi kerak. Shuning uchun quyidagi cheklolvar qo'yiladi:

1. Suv sathi bo'yicha cheklov - $h_{\min} \leq h(t) \leq h_{\max}$
2. Nasos quvvati bo'yicha cheklov - $0 \leq Q_i(t) \leq Q_{i, \max}$
3. Iste'molchilar talabi bajarilishi - $\sum_{i=1}^m Q_i(t) + Q_{res}(t) \geq D(t)$
4. Bosim cheklovi - $H_{\min} \leq H(t) \leq H_{\max}$

Chekli ayirmalar usuliga o'tish. Vaqt oralig'i $[0, T]$ teng qismlarga bo'linadi:

$$t_k = k \Delta t, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N$$

bu yerda

$$\Delta = \frac{T}{N}$$

Suv sathining hosilasi chekli ayirma bilan almashtiriladi:

$$\frac{dh(t)}{dt} \approx \frac{h_{k+1} - h_k}{\Delta t}$$

Shunda dinamik tenglama quyidagicha bo'ladi:

$$\frac{h_{k+1} - h_k}{\Delta t} = \frac{1}{S} \left(\sum_{i=1}^m Q_{i,k} - D_k \right)$$

bundan

$$h_{k+1} = h_k + \frac{\Delta t}{S} \left(\sum_{i=1}^m Q_{i,k} - D_k \right) \quad (4)$$

kelib chiqadi. (4) tenglama chekli ayirmalar usulidagi asosiy diskret model hisoblanadi [10].

Diskret maqsad funksiyasi uzluksiz integral yig'indi bilan almashtiriladi:

$$J = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \Delta t \cdot C_k \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{\rho g Q_{i,k} H_{i,k}}{\eta_i} \rightarrow \min \quad (5)$$

Agar nasoslarni tez-tez yoqib-o'chirish zararli deb hisoblansa, qo'shimcha had kiritiladi:

$$J = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \Delta t \cdot C_k \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{\rho g Q_{i,k} H_{i,k}}{\eta_i} + \lambda \sum_{k=1}^{N-1} \sum_{i=1}^m |u_{i,k} - u_{i,k-1}| \rightarrow \min \quad (6)$$

bu yerda λ -nasosni yoqib-o'chirish jarimasini bildiradi. Bu juda muhim hisoblanadi, chunki faqat energiyani minimallashtirishga qaralsa, model nasoslarni juda ko'p marta yoqib-o'chirishi mumkin. Amaliyotda bu mexanik eskirishga olib keladi [11, 12].

Yakuniy diskret masala quyidagicha yoziladi:

$$J = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \Delta t \cdot C_k \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{\rho g Q_{i,k} H_{i,k}}{\eta_i} \rightarrow \min \quad (7)$$

quyidagi shartlar ostida:

$$\begin{aligned} h_{k+1} &= h_k + \frac{\Delta t}{S} \left(\sum_{i=1}^m Q_{i,k} - D_k \right) \\ h_{\min} &\leq h_k \leq h_{\max} \\ 0 &\leq Q_{i,k} \leq Q_{i,\max} \\ u_{i,k} &\in \{0,1\} \\ Q_{i,k} &= 0, \text{ agar } u_{i,k} = 0 \\ Q_{i,k} &> 0, \text{ agar } u_{i,k} = 1 \end{aligned}$$

Bu masala aralash-butun sonli optimallashtirish masalasiga aylanadi [1, 13].

Masalani yechish algoritmini quyidagicha yozish mumkun:

1-bosqich. Boshlang'ich ma'lumotlarni kiritish

Berilgan:

- nasoslar soni;
- har bir nasosning maksimal sarfi;
- har bir nasosning FIK qiymati;
- rezervuar yuzasi;
- boshlang'ich suv sathi;
- minimal va maksimal suv sathi;
- har soatdagi suv talabi;
- har soatdagi elektr energiya tarifi.

2-bosqich. Vaqtni diskretlash

Masalan, 24 soatlik davr olinadi:

$$T = 24$$

Agar har 1 soat uchun hisob qilinsa:

$$\Delta t = 1$$

$$N = 24$$

3-bosqich. Suv sathini hisoblash

Har bir vaqt bosqichida:

$$h_{k+1} = h_k + \frac{\Delta t}{S} \left(\sum Q_{i,k} - D_k \right)$$

4-bosqich. Barcha mumkin bo'lgan nasos rejimlarini tekshirish

Masalan, 3 ta agregat bo'lsa, har bir soatda quyidagi variantlar bor:

$$(0,0,0), (1,0,0), (0,1,0), (0,0,1), (1,1,0), \dots, (1,1,1)$$

Har bir kombinatsiya uchun:

- suv yetarlimi;
 - sath me'yordami;
 - bosim yetarlimi;
 - xarajat qancha;
- tekshiriladi.

5-bosqich. Eng optimal rejim tanlanadi

Shartlarni buzmaganda eng kichik qiymatli J tanlanadi.

Misol: Faraz qilaylik

- bitta rezervuar bor;
- 2 ta agregat mavjud;
- har bir agregat soatiga $100 m^3 / soat$ uzatadi;
- rezervuar yuzasi $S = 500 m^2$;
- boshlang'ich suv sathi $h_0 = 5 m$;
- ruxsat etilgan sath:

$$3 \leq h_k \leq 8$$

- vaqt oralig'i:

$$\Delta t = 1 soat$$

- iste'mol talabi:

$$D_k = 150 m^3 / soat$$

Agar faqat bitta agregat ishlasa:

$$Q = 100$$

$$h_{k+1} = h_k + \frac{1}{500}(100 - 150)$$

$$h_{k+1} = h_k - 0,1$$

Demak, suv sathi har soatda 0.1 metrga kamayadi.

Agar ikkita nasos ishlasa:

$$Q = 200$$

$$h_{k+1} = h_k + \frac{1}{500}(200 - 150)$$

$$h_{k+1} = h_k + 0,1$$

Demak, suv sathi har soatda 0.1 metrga oshadi.

Optimal boshqaruv shundan iborat bo'ladi:

- arzon elektr tarifi vaqtida ikki nasosni ishlatib, rezervuarni to'ldirish;
- qimmat tarif vaqtida bitta nasos yoki umuman nasossiz ishlash;
- lekin suv sathi $3m$ dan pastga tushmasligi kerak.

XULOSA

Nasos stansiyalarining ishini optimal boshqarish masalasi avval differensial tenglamalar tizimi orqali modellashtirildi. So'ngra vaqt bo'yicha diskretlash amalga oshirilib, hosilalar chekli ayirmalar bilan almashtirildi. Ya'ni Nasos stansiyalar ishini optimal boshqarish masalasi chekli ayirmalar usuli yordamida uzluksiz optimal boshqaruv masalasidan diskret optimallashtirish masalasiga keltiriladi. Bunda vaqt oralig'i chekli bosqichlarga bo'linadi, suv sathining hosilasi chekli ayirma orqali ifodalanadi va rezervuardagi suv balansi algebraik rekurrent tenglama ko'rinishida yoziladi. Natijada optimal boshqarish uchun har bir vaqt bosqichida nasoslarning

yoqilgan yoki o'chirilgan holati, suv sarfi, energiya xarajati, rezervuar sathi hisoblanadi va nasoslarning ish rejimini tanlash orqali umumiy energiya xarajatini minimallashtirishga erishiladi.

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